

SOCIAL SCIENCES

INTERPROFESSIONAL COLLABORATION IN SOCIAL WORK FOR STRENGTHENING THE PSYCHOSOCIAL RESILIENCE OF CHILDREN AT SOCIAL RISK

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Abstract

This study explores the significance of interprofessional collaboration in social work for strengthening the psychosocial resilience of children at social risk. Based on data from Statistics Lithuania and recent research, the paper highlights that children growing up in socially at-risk environments often face violence, addictions, social exclusion, and adverse family conditions. Psychosocial resilience, the ability to adapt and cope with stress, becomes a key factor in ensuring their development under challenging circumstances. The research involved a survey of 125 social workers, focusing on direct and indirect intervention methods and the importance of cross-sectoral cooperation. The findings reveal that the most effective strategies are comprehensive, coordinated actions involving families, schools, and institutional support. The study confirms that a systematic, partnership-based approach not only enhances children's resilience but also contributes to creating a safe environment and fostering a positive self-image.

Keywords: Psychosocial resilience, children at social risk, interprofessional collaboration, social work, multidisciplinary intervention, child welfare.

Research Relevance

Today, the rapidly increasing scope of social risk highlights the urgent need to strengthen the psychosocial resilience of children, particularly through interinstitutional collaboration involving services for vulnerable families. According to data from the Lithuanian Department of Statistics, as many as 10,361 children from socially at-risk families received social services at children's day care centers, representing a 20% increase compared to previous years. This growth was driven by external factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic, increased domestic violence, higher levels of psychoactive substance use, social exclusion, and a lack of parenting skills. Data from 2022 indicate that this number remained stable at 10,014 children.

Children growing up in environments characterized by social risk often face obstacles to their psychological, social, and spiritual development. In such contexts, psychosocial resilience becomes especially critical defined as the capacity to cope with stress, adapt, and function under adverse conditions (8,9). Researchers argue that this resilience can be fostered through complex, multi-institutional strategies tailored to various service settings (14,17). However, a child's ability to develop these skills depends on the safety of their environment, parental behavior models, as well as influences from school and peers (12,16).

In this context, interinstitutional cooperation involving social workers, educators, and psychologists is of particular importance. Their joint efforts not only help identify risk factors but also reinforce children's capacity to form secure relationships, resist negative influences, and make constructive decisions (6,2) Scientific literature indicates that a comprehensive approach to resilience development yields significant results when implemented systematically and on an interdisciplinary basis (4,1).a

Research Problem.

Psychosocial resilience is a learned skill that enables children to adapt and respond constructively to adverse life circumstances (9,17). However, children experiencing social risk often grow up in dysfunctional environments lacking safety, emotional support, stability, and positive social role models. Emphasizes that family crises, violence, addictions, inadequate parenting skills, and the erosion of moral values directly affect children's self-perception and the development of resilience. In such contexts, children frequently experience social exclusion, severely limiting their psychosocial growth (12).

Points out that schools, as key educational institutions, do not always provide safe and supportive environments. In settings where toxic atmospheres prevail, there is an increased risk of delinquent and deviant behavior (16). Highlight the importance of peer and social relationships, noting that children lacking psychosocial skills often struggle to resist negative external influences (12). Emphasize that the development of psychosocial resilience requires coordinated collaboration among various environmental systems, including family, schools, and social service providers (11, 13).

Despite this, effective collaboration among social work professionals remains limited in practice, which constrains the implementation of long-term, child-centered strategies for resilience development (6, 8). In the absence of cohesive support and information sharing across institutions, children at social risk are often left without adequate assistance, diminishing their ability to resist negative influences and successfully integrate into society.

Research Methodology. Research Methods

The empirical research involved the completion of 125 questionnaires. A non-probability purposive sampling method was employed to select participants. Questionnaires were distributed electronically to chil-

dren's day centers, open youth spaces, and other institutions across Lithuania that provide services to children experiencing social risk. Respondents were explicitly asked to ensure that the survey would be completed only by social workers who directly work with such cases. Anonymity was ensured, and principles of confidentiality were strictly followed. Participation in the research was entirely voluntary.

A quantitative descriptive research approach was chosen to meet the research aim.

Data Collection Method

Data were collected via an online survey. The questionnaire, developed by the author of the study, was sent via email to the selected institutions. According to Gaižauskienė and Mikėnė [5], online surveys are a convenient and accessible method for collecting data. However, they emphasize that the limitations of this method must be acknowledged in order to maintain the quality and reliability of the study. These limitations include: challenges in achieving appropriate sample coverage and representativeness, lack of feedback mechanisms, and the potential for reduced control over the quality of survey responses.

Data Analysis Method. The collected data were analyzed using statistical data analysis methods. This allowed for identifying trends and associations among responses and interpreting the overall tendencies of the surveyed population.

Research Ethics. The study conducted the following six core ethical principles: confidentiality, anonymity, fairness, the right to receive accurate information, benevolence, and respect for human dignity. **Confidentiality:** The identity of the participants was kept strictly confidential. A verbal and written guarantee was provided that the collected data would be used solely for academic research purposes and would not be disclosed publicly. **Anonymity:** Participants were not required to sign or submit any personal information. The survey did not reveal the identity of any individual respondent. **Fairness:** The criteria used to select participants were clearly communicated, and the rationale for their invitation to participate was explained. **Right to Accurate**

Information: The participants were fully informed about the aim of the quantitative study and were assured that any questions would be answered promptly and transparently. **Benevolence:** All participants voluntarily study the study voluntarily and expressed their views without any pressure. Before completing the questionnaire, participants were informed that their responses would remain anonymous. **Respect for Human Dignity:** Participants were introduced to the aim of the study through neutral, objective information focused on the specificity of the research. They were assured that the research would pose no risks.

Intervention Strategies Used by Social Workers and Their Effectiveness in Fostering Children's Psychosocial Resilience

Psychosocial resilience, defined as the capacity to adapt, maintain emotional stability, and cope with stressful situations, is one of the key factors that enables children to grow and develop despite adverse life conditions [10,15]. For children raised in socially risky environments, the development of resilience becomes particularly significant, as they are often exposed to multilayered challenges such as unstable family dynamics, violence, social exclusion, addictions, and unsafe living conditions.

In such contexts, the social worker becomes one of the most crucial intermediaries in helping the child establish a positive relationship with their environment, strengthen emotional resilience, and develop the capacity to overcome psychosocial difficulties. One of the key strategies applied by social workers working with children at social risk is direct intervention [7]. This type of intervention includes identifying problems, empowering family members, providing counselling and referrals, organizing and delivering services, conducting group sessions, and offering recommendations.

Social workers were asked to indicate which direct intervention methods they most frequently apply in the development of psychosocial resilience among minors (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Most commonly used direct intervention methods by social workers in developing children's psychosocial resilience

Problem identification, applied in as much as 87% of cases, indicates that social workers primarily focus on the diagnostic function accurately determining the problems faced by children and their families. This aligns with the principles of the systemic approach to social work, which emphasize the importance of comprehensive situation analysis (3). **Counselling, empowerment of family members, and service organization** (80%) demonstrate that, in practice, social workers actively involve family members in decision-making processes and aim to implement integrated sup-

port measures. **Providing recommendations and suggestions** (68%) and **representation** (57%) reflect developmental aspects that help children understand their rights and opportunities, while also strengthening their voice within social systems. **Conducting group activities** (53%) shows that although these methods are used less frequently, they remain significant due to their ability to foster children's social skills, cooperation, and self-awareness—factors that correlate with greater resilience (1; 4).

When discussing indirect intervention methods, the statistically significant results indicate that:

Figure 2. Most effective indirect intervention methods used by social workers in developing children's psychosocial resilience

Collaboration with other specialists (75%) and the monitoring of the family and child within various systemic contexts (73%) are identified as the most effective strategies. This aligns with the emphasis in contemporary research on the necessity of interinstitutional cooperation in child welfare interventions (14; 15). The **involvement of sociocultural service providers (70%) and cooperation with children's day centres (65%)** highlight that social workers actively seek to ensure children have access to structured leisure, creative expression, and the development of social networks.

Figure 3. Social workers' assessment of the likelihood of psychosocial vulnerability among children experiencing social risk

This finding aligns with international insights highlighting that risk factors within the family, community, or institutional settings contribute to a reduced capacity in children to cope with stress (15). However, the importance of individual response is also emphasized, **not all children growing up in risk environments automatically become vulnerable**. In such cases, the **empowering stance of the social worker** and the availability of **institutional support** become particularly

Conclusions

Collaboration between various institutions involved in social work practice is a vital component in fostering psychosocial resilience among children experiencing social risk. Institutional synergy enables more effective identification of children's needs, systematic assessment of their developmental environment, and the provision of coordinated and consistent support. Such partnerships among professionals from different sectors contribute to the creation of a safe and supportive environment in which the child can develop social skills, strengthen emotional resilience, and build a positive self-concept.

The measures applied by social workers to develop children's psychosocial resilience become effective only within a harmonized, cooperation-based approach to support. Direct interventions—such as counselling or service organization—achieve meaningful impact when integrated into a broader context of collaboration between social, educational, healthcare, and cultural institutions. A child's resilience is significantly reinforced when their environment consistently and

Lower engagement levels were recorded in relation to **cooperation with law enforcement (33%) and the child rights protection service (47%)**, suggesting that these institutions are still perceived more as reactive or crisis-oriented actors rather than as part of an integrated support system.

Moreover, a significant 88% of the surveyed social workers stated that **children experiencing social risk are more likely to lack psychosocial resilience**, underscoring the urgency for comprehensive and coordinated interventions aimed at strengthening protective factors.

purposefully contributes to building emotional security, enhancing motivation, and encouraging autonomy.

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